

HISTORICAL REALITIES AND PHILOSOPHICAL IDEALS: DIALOGUES ACROSS DISCIPLINES

**INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC-PRACTICAL
CONFERENCE**

**TASHKENT, SEPTEMBER
20, 2025**

**MINISTRY OF HIGHER EDUCATION, SCIENCE
AND INNOVATION OF REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN
TASHKENT STATE UNIVERSITY
OF ORIENTAL STUDIES**

**RESEARCH CENTER FOR THE STUDY OF EASTERN
CULTURE AND HERITAGE**

**HISTORICAL REALITIES
AND PHILOSOPHICAL IDEALS: DIALOGUES ACROSS
DISCIPLINES**

**INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC-PRACTICAL
CONFERENCE**

Tashkent, September 20, 2025

International Scientific-Practical Conference “Historical realities and philosophical ideals: dialogues across disciplines”[Text]/ – Tashkent: Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies, 2025. -698 p.

This collection contains the materials of the international scientific-practical conference “Historical Realities and Philosophical Ideals: Dialogues Across Disciplines.” The volume includes articles dedicated to the theoretical and practical issues of interdisciplinary approaches in historical research, the history of the interconnected development of Eastern regions, current problems of historical source studies and historiography, the significance of interdisciplinary studies in exploring tangible and intangible cultural heritage, as well as the main directions of Eastern philosophy and culture. The authors of the articles are leading experts in their respective fields and young researchers.

Chief editor:

Mirzohid Askarov

Editorial board:

B.Zokirov, Sh.Yodgorov, M.Khubbaliyeva, M.Turdikhujayeva, M.Nabiyev, R.Isakov, G.Abduvakhobova, Sh.Abdurasulov, G.Jumayev

The conference materials were reviewed by the Academic Council of the Faculty of “Eastern Civilization and Philosophy” at Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies and recommended for publication (No. 3, dated October 23, 2025).

O'ZBEKISTONDAGI AN'ANAVIY KULOLCHILIK MAKTABLARINING BARQAROR TURIZM RIVOJLANISHIDAGI ROLI

Bobir Odilov

Toshkent davlat sharqshunoslik universiteti dotsenti, PhD

Kalit so'zlar: an'anaviy kulolchilik, barqaror turizm, madaniy meros, hunar-mandchilik maktablari, O'zbekiston.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistondagi an'anaviy kulolchilik maktablarining barqaror turizm rivojlanishidagi o'rni yoritiladi. Kulolchilikning qadimiy ildizlari, tarixiy taraqqiyoti hamda mahalliy maktablarning shakllanish jarayoni tahlil qilingan. Mustaqillikdan keyingi davrda Rishton, G'ijduvon, Xiva, Samarqand, Shahrisabz, Toshkent va Urgut kulolchilik maktablarining qayta tiklanishi va ularning turizm bilan integratsiyasi ko'rsatib berilgan. An'anaviy kulolchilik barqaror turizm tamoyillari – iqtisodiy rivojlanish, madaniy merosni asrash, ekologik muvozanatni saqlash va mahalliy hamjamiyatlarni qo'llab-quvvatlashda muhim omil sifatida baholangan.

THE ROLE OF TRADITIONAL POTTERY SCHOOLS IN UZBEKISTAN IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SUSTAINABLE TOURISM

Bobir Odilov

Associate Professor, PhD, Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies

Key words: traditional pottery, sustainable tourism, cultural heritage, craft schools, Uzbekistan

Abstract: This article explores the role of traditional pottery schools in Uzbekistan in the development of sustainable tourism. It highlights the ancient roots and historical evolution of pottery, as well as the formation of local schools. The paper emphasizes the revival of pottery traditions in the post-independence period, focusing on the Rishton, Gijduvon, Khiva, Samarkand, Shahrisabz, Tashkent, and Urgut schools, and their integration with tourism. Traditional pottery is assessed as a significant factor in promoting sustainable tourism principles, including economic development, cultural heritage preservation, ecological balance, and support for local communities.

So'nggi yillarda dunyo miqyosida turizm sanoati barqaror rivojlanish konsepsiyasi asosida shakllanib bormoqda. Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkiloti, Jahon Turizm Tashkiloti (UNWTO) va boshqa xalqaro institutlar barqaror turizmni XXI asrning eng muhim

yo'nalishlaridan biri sifatida belgilamoqda. O'zbekistonda ham barqaror turizm nafaqat iqtisodiy foyda keltiruvchi soha, balki ijtimoiy adolatni qaror toptirish, ekologik muvozanatni saqlash va madaniy merosni asrashga xizmat qiluvchi jarayon sifatida qaralib, turizmni rivojlantirish strategiyasida asosiy mezonlardan biri sifatida belgilangan.

Bugungi kunda barqaror turizm tamoyillarini an'anaviy kulolchilik maktablari misolida kuzatsak, ular mahalliy aholi uchun yangi ish o'rinlari yaratish, hunar sirlarini yosh avlodga o'tkazish, hunarmandchilik mahsulotlarini sotish orqali iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish, milliy qadriyatlarni asrab-avaylash va targ'ib qilish, tabiiy resurslardan oqilona foydalanish va atrof-muhitga zarar yetkazmaslik kabi muhim vazifalarni bajarishini ko'ramiz. Mustaqillik yillarida qayta tiklangan an'anaviy kulolchilik maktablari aynan shu yo'nalishlarda ijobiy natijalarga erishib, kulolchilikning barqaror turizm rivojlanishidagi o'rnini yaqqol ko'rsatib bermoqda.

Barqaror turizmni samarali tashkil etishda kulolchilikning o'rnini to'liq anglash uchun, avvalo, yurtimizda kulolchilik maktablarining shakllanish va rivojlanish tarixiga e'tibor qaratish lozim. Kulolchilik — boshqa xalqlar singari bizning jamiyat uchun ham uzoq tarixiy jarayonni anglatib, ajdodlarimizning boy qadriyatlari turli davr va omillar ta'sirida shakllanib va rivojlanib kelganini ko'rsatadi. Bu jarayon tariximizning turli davrlarida mahalliy aholining ma'lum qismini ish bilan ta'minlagan, xalq merosini asrab-avaylash va yosh avlodga yetkazishda asosiy poydevor bo'lgan, shu bilan birga, aholiga ekologik toza mahsulot yetkazib berishda ham muhim o'rin tutgan.

Arxeologik tadqiqotlar ko'rsatadiki, O'zbekiston hududida kulolchilik miloddan avvalgi II ming yillikdayoq shakllangan. Qadimgi Sug'diyona, Baqtriya, Xorazm va Farg'ona vodiysi hududlarida topilgan sopol buyumlar bu hunarning uzoq tarixiy ildizlarga ega ekanidan dalolat beradi. Arxeologlar A.Asqarov, T.Shirinov, B.Matboboyev, A. Anorboyev, G.Shishkina, san'atshunoslar A.Hakimov, E.Gyul va boshqalar tadqiqotlarida qayd etilganidek, neolit davrida kulolchilik dastgohining ixtiro qilinishi buyumlarning dag'allikdan san'at darajasiga ko'tarilishiga xizmat qilgan. Antik davrga kelib, yunon madaniyati ta'sirida buyumlarning shakli va tasviriy yechimlari o'zgarib bordi. VIII asrda esa kulolchilikda muhim burilish yasagan sirlash texnologiyasi qo'llanila boshladi¹.

¹ Костенко Л. Ф. Путешествие в Бухару русской миссии в 1871 г. СПб. – с. 26.; Головин Г. Кустарные промыслы Туркестана // «Туркестанский сборник». Т. 512. Ташкент, 1909. – с. 26.; Развадовский В. Опыт

Somoniylar davrida arab yozuvida bitilgan hikmatli soʻzlar tushirilgan sopol buyumlar hukmdorlar saroyida oʻz oʻrnini topdi¹. Amir Temur va temuriylar davrida xorijiy ustalarning kirib kelishi natijasida kulolchilikda qoʻllaniladigan ranglar boyidi. Buyuk Ipak yoʻlining rivojlanishi esa oʻrta asrlarda kulolchilik buyumlari turlarining kengayishiga bevosita taʼsir koʻrsatdi. Binokorlikning rivojlanishi koshinkorlik tarmogʻining taraqqiyotiga turtki berib, kulolchilik maktablarining shakllanishiga sabab boʻldi. Mintaqalarda vujudga kelgan lokal maktablar nafaqat uy-roʻzgʻor buyumlari ishlab chiqarish vositasi, balki xalqning estetik didi, diniy qarashlari, urf-odatlar va madaniy qadriyatlarini mujassamlashtiruvchi maʼnaviy meros sifatida shakllandi.

Bir soʻz bilan aytganda, uzoq tarixiy jarayonlar kulol ustalarning jamiyatdagi maqomini belgilab, ustoz-shogird munosabatlarini shakllantirdi, xalqning nozik didini rivojlantirdi va hunar sirlarining avloddan-avlodga uzatilishini taʼminladi. Ushbu jarayonlarni bugungi kunda barqaror turizmning asosiy tamoyillari bilan uygʻun holda baholash mumkin.

Bugungi kungacha toʻplangan maʼlumotlar kulolchilikning ilk maktablari shakllanishini toʻliq ochib bera olmasada, mavjud manbalar bu maktablardagi ijtimoiy jarayonlarni tasavvur qilishga imkon beradi. Xususan, soʻnggi oʻrta asrlarda yaratilgan va ustalarning asosiy dasturi

исследования гончарного и некоторых других кустарных промыслов в Туркестанском крае // «Туркестанское сельское хозяйство», 1916, №8. – с. 710.; Денике Б. Искусство Средней Азии. М., 1927, стр. 46–47.; Пугаченкова Г. А. Глазурованная керамика Нисы XV–XVI вв. // Труды ЮТАКЭ. Т. I. Ашхабад, 1949, с. 415, рис. 14.; Пугаченкова Г.А. Самаркандская керамика XV века. Труды Среднеазиатского государственного университета, вып. XI. Ташкент, 1950, стр. 91–120.; Воробьева М.Г. Изображение львов на ручках сосудов из Хорезма // Краткие сообщения Института этнографии им. Миклухо-Маклай. Вып. XXX. М.: Изд-во АН СССР, 1958. С. 40-53.; Пещерева Е.М. Гончарное производство Средней Азии. М.-Л. 1959. - с. 202; Рахимов М.К. Художественная керамика Узбекистана. Ташкент, 1961, стр. 23.; Ахраров И. Средневековые чернильницы с городища Кува // ОНУ, 1962, № 1. – с. 61–62.; Пугаченкова Г., Ремпель Л. История искусств Узбекистана с древнейших времен до середины XIX века. М., 1965, стр. 6.; Сайко, Э. История технологии керамического ремесла Средней Азии VIII–XII вв. / Э. Сайко. — Душанбе : Изд-во АН ТаджССР, 1966. — 211 с.; Ташходжаев, Ш. Художественная поливная керамика Самарканда (IX — начало XIII вв.) / Ш. Ташходжаев. — Ташкент : Фан, 1967. — 184 с.; Литвинский Б.А. Древние кочевники «Крыши мира». М., 1972. – с. 42–43.; Андреев М. С., Чехович О. Д. Арк Бухары в конце XIX – начале XX вв. Душанбе, 1972. – с. 106.; Шаниязов К. Ш. К этнической истории узбекского народа. Ташкент, 1974. – с. 280.; Дервиз Г., Жадова Л., Жданко И., Митлянский Д. Современная керамика народных мастеров Средней Азии. М., 1974. – с. 235.; Шишкина, Г. Глазурованная керамика Согда (вторая половина VIII — начало XIII вв.) / Г. Шишкина. — Ташкент : Фан, 1979. — 165 с.; Ильясова С. Р., Хакимов А.А. Голубая керамика Ферганы. Риштанский мастер Шарафитдин Юсупов. М., 2015. – с. 56–58.; Ильясов Дж. Я., Имамбердыев Р. А, Исхакова Е. А. «Нет блага в богатстве...». Глазурованная керамика Ташкентского оазиса IX–XII веков. М., Фонд Марджани, 2016. С. 170.; Rishton kulolochiligi: kecha, bugun, ertaga: xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya materiallari / masʼul muharrir: Elmira Gʻul. – Fargʻona: «Fargʻona» nashriyoti, 2023. – 140 b.; Шоназаров К.Р. Узбекский народный орнамент этнографический источник. Эл. ресурс Узбекский народный орнамент этнографический источник (cyberleninka.ru) Murojaat vaqti: 28 avgust 2025.

¹ Шишкина, Г. Глазурованная керамика Согда (вторая половина VIII — начало XIII вв.) / Г. Шишкина. — Ташкент : Фан, 1979. — 165 с.

hisoblangan “Risola”lar kulol ustalarining jamiyatdagi o‘rni, ustoz-shogird munosabatlari hamda kasbga bo‘lgan hurmatni yoritib, mintaqa kulollari uchun umumiy qadriyatlarni shakllantirishga xizmat qilgan¹.

XX asrga kelib esa siyosiy va iqtisodiy o‘zgarishlar kulolchilik maktablarining inqirozga yuz tutishiga sabab bo‘ldi. Ishlab chiqarishda zamonaviy texnologiyalarning keng qo‘llanilishi, ustaxonalarining faoliyati cheklanib sex va uyushmalarga aylantirilishi, xorijiy fabrikalarda tayyorlangan mahsulotlarning katta hajmda import qilinishi natijasida mahalliy kulol mahsulotlariga talab keskin kamaydi. Bu jarayon kulolchilik maktablarining yo‘qolishiga, hunar sirlarining uzluksiz uzatilishi va qadriyatlarning davomiyligida uzilishlarga olib keldi.

Biroq, mustaqillik yillarida bozor munosabatlarining shakllanishi, ish o‘rinlari yaratishga bo‘lgan ehtiyoj, xalqaro aloqalarning kengayishi va turizmni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan siyosat an’anaviy qadriyatlarni, jumladan kulolchilik maktablarini qayta tiklashga zamin yaratdi. Bugungi kunda bu jarayon usta kulol avlodlari, ularning shogirdlari va sohaga qiziqqan yangi avlod vakillari tomonidan amalga oshirilmoqda.

An’anaviy kulolchilikda mahsulot yaratish jarayoni asosan qo‘l mehnatiga asoslangan bo‘lib, murakkab bosqichlarni o‘z ichiga oladi: tuproq tanlash, loy tayyorlash, shakl berish, quritish, angob va rang uchun tabiiy xom ashyolar yig‘ish, naqsh tushirish, pishirish. Bundan tashqari, ustalar mahsulotni sotish va iqtisodiy faoliyatni boshqarish mas’uliyatini ham o‘z zimmasiga olgan.

Ana shunday murakkab jarayonlarni o‘zida mujassamlashtirgan kulolchilikning an’anaviy maktablari bugungi kunda tiklanib, Rishton, G‘ijduvon, Xiva, Toshkent, Shahrisabz, Samarqand va Urgut an’analari asosida rivojlanmoqda. Bu maktablar nafaqat amaliy san’at yodgorligi, balki turizmni rivojlantirishda muhim resurs sifatida qaralmoqda. Chunki kulolchilikning o‘ziga xosligi, tabiiyligi, mahalliyliги va tarixiyliги xorijiy sayyohlarni jalb qiluvchi asosiy omillardandir.

Hozirgi kunda O‘zbekistonda kulolchilik maktablari tarixiy ildizlarga tayangan holda qayta tiklanib, turizm bilan uzviy bog‘langan holda rivojlanmoqda. Mintaqalarda shakllangan kulolchilik maktablari o‘ziga xos lokal xususiyatlari bilan ajralib turadi va ular mahalliy

¹ Dala yozuvi, Horazm. 2025. Risola. 1951 yil 26 martda Rayimberdi Muhammadjon boboning o‘g‘li, yozuvchi Egamberdi bobo Avazniyoz bobo o‘g‘li tomonidan arab tilidan tarjima qilingan. Usta kulol otasi tomonidan Odil Matchonovga taqdim etilgan va hozirda nabirasi Og‘abek Matchonov foydalanib kelmoqda.

iqtisodiyot, madaniy meros hamda barqaror turizmni rivojlantirishda muhim o'rin tutmoqda.

Rishton kulolchilik maktabi Farg'ona vodiysida shakllangan bo'lib, uning eng asosiy belgisi ishqorli sir va ko'k rangning soyalari hisoblanadi. Bu maktab buyumlarida nozik devorli idishlar, silliq yuzalar va nafis naqshlar uchraydi. Hozirgi kunda an'analarni tiklash kesimida yuzasiga oqtoшни tabiiy giyoh siri bilan qorishtirilgan silliq bo'lmagan sirlash tehnologiyasidan ham foydalanilmoqda¹. Rishton kulollari bugungi kunda master-klasslar, tajriba uchun ustaxonalar va interaktiv mashg'ulotlar orqali nafaqat an'anani davom ettirmoqda, balki sayyohlarni ham faol jalb qilmoqda. "Moviy Rishton" brendi xalqaro miqyosda mashhur bo'lib, turizmning samarali omiliga aylangan.

So'nggi yillarda Rishton tumaniga mahalliy va xorijiy sayyohlar tashrifi sezilarli darajada ortgani kuzatilmoqda. Sayyohlar tashrifining asosiy yo'nalishi kulolchilik amaliyotini bevosita kuzatish hamda usta hunarmandlar tomonidan yaratilgan san'at asarlarini xarid qilishdan iboratligi alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi. Amaliy kuzatuvlar va o'tkazilgan so'rovnoma natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, hududda faoliyat yuritayotgan Alisher Nazirov an'anaviy kulolchilik maktabi ustaxonasiga 2025 yilning 8 oyi davomida 1000 nafarga yaqin xorijiy va 3000 nafardan ziyod mahalliy sayyoh tashrif buyurgan².

G'ijduvon kulolchilik maktabi Buxoro viloyatida faoliyat yuritib, an'anaviy iliq ranglar (sariq, jigarrang, yashil) hamda geometrik naqshlarning ko'pligi bilan mashhurdir. Bu maktab buyumlari orasida katta laganlar, likob, lagan, suviner va maishiy idishlar keng tayyorlanadi. Bugungi kunda G'ijduvondagi ustaxona-muzeylar turistlarga naqsh chizish bo'yicha mashg'ulotlar taklif qilib, kulolchilikni gastronomiya va turizm bilan uyg'unlashtirmoqda.

Xiva (Xorazm) kulolchilik maktabi zangori ranglarning ustunligi, naqshlarda esa me'moriy koshinkorlik elementlarining ko'pligi bilan ajralib turadi. Bu maktab buyumlari ko'proq monumental ruhga ega bo'lib, epigrafik yozuvlar ham uchraydi. Honqa va Kattabog' hududidagi ustaxonalar turistlarga tarixiy muhitda kulolchilik san'atini ko'rsatib, tirik meros sifatida xizmat qilmoqda.

Samarqand kulolchilik maktabi ko'k-oq-qora kontrast ranglari bilan ajralib turib, temuriylar davri estetikasi va astronomik ramzlarni eslatadi. Bu maktab buyumlari orasida choyxona idishlari, interyer

¹ Dala yozuvi. 2025.

² Dala yozuvi. 2025.

panellari keng tarqalgan. Samarqand kulolchilik ustaxonalari bugungi kunda tarixiy marshrutlar — Registon, Shohi Zinda va boshqa yodgorliklar bilan uyg'un holda turistlarga taqdim etilmoqda.

Shahrisabz kulolchilik maktabi asosan amaliy-maishiy buyumlari bilan mashhur. Mustahkam va qulay idishlar, suv saqlash ko'zalarining soddaligi bu maktabning asosiy xususiyatidir. Bugungi kunda ustozshogird an'anasi asosida tiklanib, mahalliy bozor va turizm ehtiyojlariga moslashmoqda.

Toshkent kulolchilik maktabi esa an'anani zamonaviy dizayn bilan uyg'unlashtirishi bilan ajralib turadi. Minimalizm, funkcionallik va yangi dizayn yechimlari mahsulotlarni shahar interyerlari va restoran-kafelar uchun moslashtiradi. Hozirda Toshkentda kulollar dizaynerlar bilan hamkorlik qilib, galereya va ko'rgazmalar orqali turizm bozoriga chiqmoqda.

Urgut kulolchilik maktabi (Samarqand viloyati) utilitar va dekorativ jihatlarni uyg'unlashtirgan bo'lib, asosan xo'jalik idishlari, gul tuvaklari va suvenirilar bilan mashhur. Urgut bozori bilan uzviy bog'langan bu maktab bugungi kunda sayyohlar uchun tezkor tajriba paketlari taklif qilmoqda¹.

Umuman olganda, O'zbekistondagi hozirgi kulolchilik maktablari nafaqat milliy hunarmandchilik merosini saqlab qolmoqda, balki turizmning barqaror rivojlanishida ham muhim omilga aylangan. Ularning rang palitrasi, naqsh tili, funkcionallik yo'nalishi va turizm integratsiyasi bir-biridan farqlanib, sayyohlar uchun xilma-xil tajriba yaratmoqda.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Odilov, B., Doniyorov, A., Sayfullaev, D., Karimov, N., Juraev, S., Zokirov, B., & Sattorova, Z. Cybersecurity Challenges for Ethnotourism Operators: Strategies for Protection.
2. Bobir, O. (2019). Study of traditional irrigation system in Uzbekistan (In the exemple of the investigations of the second half of XIX century and XX century). Scientific Journal, 2(12), 85-95.
3. Odilov, B. (2018). Characteristics of economic activity of the population of Fergana valley in XIX and at the beginning of XX centuries. International Journal of Development Rezerch (IJDR), 8(10), 23827-23829.
4. Allabergenov, M., Mustafaeva, S., Ziyamukhamedov, J., Yusupov, S., Khalimova, F., Madrahimova, G., ... & Sattorova, Z. (2024). Intelligent Educational Environments and Ubiquitous Computing for Continuous Learning and Digital Literacy Development. J. Wirel. Mob. Networks Ubiquitous Comput. Dependable Appl., 15(4), 179-191.

¹ Dala yozuvi. 2025.

CONTENTS

PREFACE.....	3
--------------	---

SESSION №1

THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL ISSUES OF INTERDISCIPLINARY APPROACHES IN HISTORICAL RESEARCH

<i>Iskhakov M.</i> Social anthropology, its interdisciplinary scientific and educational features.....	5
<i>Doniyorov A.</i> Historical roots of interethnic harmony and tolerance in Uzbekistan.....	11
<i>Khaydarov I.</i> The industry of Uzbekistan during the “perestroika” policy (1985–1990).....	20
<i>Khaydarov I., Ruzikulova Z.</i> The economic crisis of the Timurid empire and its social consequences.....	28
<i>Rasulova N.</i> Views on the formation of political parties and their theoretical-conceptual foundations.....	38
<i>Alimova R.</i> The significance of interdisciplinary approaches in studying the history of foreign trade relations of the Bukhara emirate in the early 20th century.....	49
<i>Madraimov A.</i> Shahrukh Mirza and the sending of the kiswah for the Kaaba: religious, political, and cultural significance.....	57
<i>Madraimov A., Eshmurodov B.</i> Strict discipline and personnel policy in the army of Amir Temur.....	62
<i>Askarov M.</i> The level of study of the topic of modern uzbek identity.....	74
<i>Zokirov B.</i> On interdisciplinary approaches to the study of ethnotoponyms.....	81
<i>Pardayev M.</i> Archaeological research conducted in the Sokh basin.....	89
<i>Sharifiy N.</i> A glance at the history of the spiritual administration of muslims of Central Asia and Kazakhstan.....	103
<i>Gaziyeva G.</i> Relations between Uzbekistan and Saudi Arabia in the context of interdisciplinary research and trans-civilizational cooperation.....	110

SESSION №2

GLOBAL HISTORY: THE INTERCONNECTED DEVELOPMENT OF EASTERN REGIONS

<i>Madraimov A.</i> Historical realities and philosophical ideals in the era of the Timurids and Boburids: interdisciplinary dialogues.....	119
<i>Abdullayev N., Abdimanapova F.</i> Political instability in Turkey between 1970 and 1980 and its consequences.....	125

<i>Khodjimuratova D.</i> Methodological approaches to studying the transformation of political systems in theocratic states.....	134
<i>Azimov K.</i> Problems of shared water usage in the middle east region: a brief history of joint water utilization in the Nile river basin.....	140
<i>Khudayberdiyev A.</i> The role of Iran in the Yemeni civil war.....	148
<i>Abdazimov J.</i> The formation of comprehensive strategic partnership relations between Uzbekistan and China in the new era.....	155
<i>Khubbalieva M.</i> Chinese sources and travelogues related to the history of Central Asia.....	164
<i>Rizayev A.</i> Conceptual and theoretical foundations of Arab national identity.....	173
<i>Yodgorov Sh.</i> The impact of radical islamic organizations in Egypt on national security and stability (late 20th - early 21st century).....	185
<i>Tukhtasinova Sh.</i> Causes and consequences of feminist movements in Pakistan.....	197
<i>Kobilova G.</i> Specific features of the soft power strategy in the Republic of Korea's foreign policy.....	203
<i>Sharafova D.</i> Political and social causes in the formation of migration in North African countries.....	210
<i>Taylakov T.</i> Debates about Israeli democracy.....	215
<i>Kalandarov U.</i> Water issue in Iran–Afghanistan relations.....	228
<i>Berdikulov D.</i> Iran's instruments of power in the Middle East region (the case of non-state actors in Lebanon).....	239
<i>Bakhodirkhonov U.</i> The “Taliban” factor in Saudi Arabia's relations with Afghanistan.....	244
<i>Rakhmatov Kh.</i> Uzbekistan and The Uae: priority directions and prospects for cooperation.....	248
<i>Akhmadov N.</i> Transnational history and migration.....	256
<i>Khodjimuratova D., Abduolimova D.</i> The impact of religion on Iran's domestic and foreign policy.....	264

SESSION №3

CURRENT ISSUES IN HISTORICAL SOURCE STUDIES AND HISTORIOGRAPHY

<i>Shadmanova S.</i> Through visual sources: research on history and society in Uzbekistan, late 19th – 20th century.....	274
<i>Saidov Sh.</i> Study of Khorezm–Russia relations in the soviet period: approaches and interpretations.....	289
<i>Mirzaev N.</i> The <i>Waqfnama</i> of Mawlana Muhammad Sharif as a primary source for the social history of 17 th century Bukhara.....	297
<i>Akhmedov M.</i> Persian sources on the history of India in the pre-mughal period.....	302

Turayev L. Contemporary topical issues of historical source studies and historiography.....	315
Askarov M., Mamadalikhojiyeva Sh. Application of gender theory in historical-ethnographic research: innovations and challenges.....	320
Khudayorov A. X. Contemporary issues of historiography and source studies and prospects for development.....	328
Sangirov J. Relations between the Ashtarkhanids and The Ottomans.....	333
Abdukhalilova A. Analysis of tax terminology in the documents of the Khiva Khanate.....	344
Turdikhojayeva M. Approaches to the historiography of the heavenly horses of Dovon.....	349
Hasanova S. The rebellion led by Haji Davud khan in Azerbaijan during the early decades of the 18th century (based on soviet historiography).....	360
Abdullayev J., Jo'arakulova M. Narshakhī's "History of Bukhara": its study in source studies and historiography.....	370
Hamidova N. The Seljuk state organization in Fazlullah Rashid al-din's Jami al-Tawarikh.....	380
Nabiyev M. Boris Yakovlevich Staviskiy and the ancient archaeological heritage of Surkhandarya.....	389
Abdurasulov Sh. Analysis of Central Asian sufi scholars and their scientific heritage in the works of Annemarie Schimmel.....	399
Sherkhanov S. The historical reality and philosophical ideals of Central Asian cities in the works of Yaqut al-Hamawi.....	411
Ergasheva M. Analysis of ethnic changes and interethnic processes in the Zarafshan valley in the 19th – early 20th centuries.....	426

SESSION №4

THE IMPORTANCE OF INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH IN THE STUDY OF TANGIBLE AND INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE

Rostami M., Janpourtaher M. Reflection of the tangible and intangible heritage of textiles in the historical relations between Iran and Uzbekistan and its role in the development of regional intractions.....	434
Nazarova S. Reflection of intangible heritage in the works of Abdulla Qodiriy.....	452
Odilov B. The role of traditional pottery schools in Uzbekistan in the development of sustainable tourism.....	460

Abirov V. Anthropological approaches to the study of tangible cultural heritage traditions.....	467
Abirov V., Nazarov M. Traditional men's clothing and its socio-cultural expression (on the example of 20th-century Central Asia).....	478
Botirova D. Psychological analysis of developing aesthetic taste and creative ability (on the example of pottery art).....	490
Shosaidov A. Information on the traditional economic culture of the peoples of Central Asia in archival documents.....	495
Isakov R. On research into the social structure of the Uzbeks in the Amudarya delta (based on the materials of the Khorezm archaeological-ethnographic expedition).....	502
Nursoatov S. Interpretation of family crafts in Turan in the middle ages (based on "Travels of Ibn Battuta").....	510
Avloqulov B. Methodology for creating a national digital catalog of intangible cultural heritage objects in Uzbekistan.....	516

SESSION №5

KEY DIRECTIONS IN EASTERN PHILOSOPHY AND CULTURE

Kodirov M. The formation of islamic sources and sciences in Eastern civilization.....	523
Izzetova E., Omonova M. Social-cultural identity as a factor of intercultural communication (on the example of Japan).....	530
Saydalieva N. The role of Farabi in the cultural and civilizational unification of the peoples of the East.....	541
Kashmeri M. Bhagavad Gita as a bridge: historical and philosophical encounters between Bharat and Central Asian civilizations.....	548
Sulaymonov J. Analysis of factors affecting social development in Ibn Khaldun's "Muqaddima".....	565
Ikramova I. Comparative study of the philosophical views of Ibn Rushd and Thomas Aquinas.....	571
Jurayev Sh. The global significance of Ibn Sina's scientific legacy.....	580
Sulaymonova Sh. Social significance and praxiological aspects of Ibn Miskawayh's concept of personal performance.....	589
Ismoilov Sh. Navigating the depths of Iqbal's philosophy: a socio-religious voyage.....	603
Jurayev M. Religious-ideological environment and scientific centers of Maverannahr in the 9th–10th centuries.....	613
Mardonova M. Jaloliddin Rumi and western scholars shared ideas on spiritual existence: the development of their views on society.....	620
Abdulfattayeva Sh. The idea of islamic reform in the worldview of Fitr'at.....	626

<i>Pulatova S.</i> Study of human will, freedom of choice, and responsibility in Nasafi's existential approach.....	631
<i>Salimov Sh.</i> Confucian values and the synthesis of democracy: the identity of civil society.....	638
<i>Ergasheva B.</i> The issue of raising girls in Eastern philosophy and culture.....	645
<i>Izzetova E., Shomukimov L.</i> Philosophical and retrospective analysis of the modernizing concept of Ismail Gasprinsky in the context of the development of jadidism in Central Asia.....	654
<i>Izzetova E., Mamadaliev A.</i> Philosophical analysis of the moral aspects of Fariduddin Attor's gnoseological concept.....	666
<i>Ikramova I., Rashidova Kh.</i> Abu Ali Ibn Sina's gnoseological and anthropological views.....	676
<i>Pulatova M., Jalolkhonov A.</i> Three hundred Kufi Qaf.....	683
<i>Pulatova M., Tursunboyev A.</i> The role of the Qur'an and hadith in eastern philosophy and culture.....	689